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COMPARATIVE PHARMACOGNOSTICAL EVALUATION OF MARKET SAMPLE OF SITOPALADI CHURNA WITH IT'S REFERANCE STANDARD

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Abstract

Background: *Sitopaladi Churna* is one of the important herbal formulations of Ayurveda. It is the combination of *Sitopala* (*Sachharum officinarum* Linn.), *Vamsalochana* (*Bambusa arundinacea* (Retz.) Willd.), *Pippali* (*Piper longum* L.), *Ela* (*Elettaria cardamomum* (L.) Maton) and *Twak* (*Cinamonum verum* J.S.Presl). To ensure the therapeutic efficacy and safety of herbal formulations and to justify their use in healthcare, standardization of these formulations is a crucial and necessary.

Material & Method: Powder microscopy of *Sitopaladi Churna* procured from the market of Vadodara, Gujarat, India was carried out at Pharmacognosy laboratory, Upgraded department of *Dravyaguna Vijnan*, Government ayurved college, Vadodara. Slides of *Sitopaladi Churna* were prepared using the required reagent and observed under the microscope.

Observation & Result: Powder microscopy of *Sitopaladi Churna* shows the presence of profound Starch grains suggests that it contains *Sitopala* (*Sachharum officinarum* Linn.); presence of stone cells, starch grains, fragments of thin walled cells and multicellular trichomes suggests it contains *Pippali* (*Piper longum* L.); presence of epidermal cells, schlerenchyma of testa, parenchymatous cells of the perisperm prisms and red coloured schlerenchymatous cells suggests it contains *Ela* (*Elettaria cardamomum* (L.) Maton), fibres, starch grains, sclereids, phloem parenchyma and vessel fragments shows presence of *Twak* (*Cinamonum verum* J.S.Presl) as its ingredients. But absence of oil globules suggest that exhausted ingredients can be adulterated with it. Presence of siliceous crystals and rosette crystals, suggests that it contains *Vamsalochana* (*Bambusa arundinacea* (Retz.) Willd.) but difficult to differentiate with highly adulterated silica.

Discussion and Conclusion: The microscopic features which were observed in the *Sitopaladi Churna* procured from the market revealed that it contains *Sitopala* (*Sachharum officinarum* Linn.), *Pippali* (*Piper longum* L.), *Ela* (*Elettaria cardamomum* (L.) Maton) and *Twak* (*Cinamonum verum* J.S.Presl) as its ingredient. Presence of siliceous crystals and rosette crystals, suggests that it contains *Vamsalochana* (*Bambusa arundinacea* (Retz.) Willd.) but difficult to differentiate with highly adulterated silica.

Key Words:

Sitopaladi Churna, Powder microscopy, standardization of herbal formulations

INTRODUCTION:

Demand for Ayurvedic formulations is increasing in the domestic market as well as internationally. Due to rapidly increasing demand, there is tremendous pressure on the supply base. Drug manufacturers make use of alternative species when the first choice is no longer available. Further, there are concerns about maintaining the qualities of supplies. In the present study, one of the most important herbal formulations of Ayurveda, *Sitopaladi Churna* is selected. *Sitopaladi Churna* is a group of drugs which consists *Sitopala* (*Sachharum officinarum* Linn.), *Vamsalochana* (*Bambusa arundinacea* (Retz.) Willd.), *Pippali* (*Piper longum* L.), *Ela* (*Elettaria cardamomum* (L.) Maton) and *Twak* (*Cinamonum verum* J.S.Presl)¹. This herbal formulation is widely used internally in range of disorders like *Kasa*, *Shwas*, disorders of *Kapha*, *Suptjihwa*, *Arochaka*, *Alpagni*, *Pashwashoola*, etc. *Vamsalochana* (Eye of the bamboo) is the siliceous materials generally found in the culms of bamboo. The silica is predominant in *Vamsalochana* and is substantially used as substitute and adulterant substance but there is no clear valid document to fulfil the use of it. The ingredients sodium silicate and ammonium silicate are used to make artificial *Vamsalochana*². So, to ensure the quality and standards of the sample of *Sitopaladi Churna* procured from the open market of Vadodara city, Gujarat, India, along with the identification of characteristic feature of each ingredient of the combination in the sample, which enables us to identify the presence or absence of any adulterant and contaminant in the market sample.

AIM:

To study the powder microscopic features of *Sitopaladi Churna* procured from the open market of Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

OBJECTIVE:

1. To study the powder microscopic features of *Sitopaladi Churna* procured from the market of Vadodara, Gujarat, India
2. To compare the assessed features of the *Sitopaladi Churna* formulation with their standards of each of the individual ingredient mentioned in authentic reference.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The sample of *Sitopaladi Churna* was procured from the market of Vadodara, Gujarat, India in the month of October 2024. The study was performed at Pharmacognosy Laboratory of Upgraded Department of *Dravyaguna Vijnana*, Government Ayurved College, Vadodara, Gujarat.

Slide preparation:

Slide of *Sitopaladi Churna* procured from the market was prepared using required reagent (Safranin and Iodine) and observed under the microscope to assess their various microscopic features. Microscopic characters observed were compared with the standards mentioned in reference standards.

OBSERVATIONS & DISCUSSION:**Table No. 1: Powder Microscopic features of *Sitopaladi Churna* found in Market Sample**

NO.	Microscopic features	<i>Sitopala</i> (<i>Sachharum officinarum</i> Linn.)	<i>Vamsalochana</i> (<i>Bambusa arundinacea</i> (Retz.) Willd.)	<i>Pippali</i> (<i>Piper longum</i> L.)	<i>Ela</i> (<i>Elettaria cardamomum</i> (L.) Maton)	<i>Twak</i> (<i>Cinamonum verum</i> J.S.Presl)
1.	Starch grains	+	-	+	-	+

2.	Fibre	-	-	-	-	+
3.	Cork cells	-	-	-	-	
4.	Prismatic crystals of calcium oxalates	-	-	-	-	-
5.	Vessel fragments	-	-	-	-	+
6.	Stone cells	-	-	+	-	-
7.	Multicellular trichomes	-	-	+	-	-
8.	Epidermal cells	-	-	-	+	-
9.	Schlerenchyma of testa	-	-	-	+	-
10.	Parenchymatous cells of the perisperm with prisms	-	-	-	+	-
11.	Red coloured schlerenchymatous cells	-	-	-	+	-
12.	Minute crystals of calcium oxalates	+	-	-	+	-
13.	Acicular crystals of calcium oxalates	-	-	-	-	-
14.	Siliceous crystals	-	+	-	-	-
15.	Phloem parenchyma	-	-	-	-	+
16.	Sclereids	-	-	-	-	+

- Absent, + Present

Table No. 2: Microscopic features in reference standard compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Sitopala (Sachharum officinarum Linn.)* found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Sitopala (Sachharum officinarum Linn.)</i> in authentic reference	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Starch grains	+	[Fig. 1.a]
2.	Crystals of calcium oxalate	+	[Fig. 1.b]

- Absent, + Present

Table No. 3: Microscopic features in reference standard³ compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Vamsalochana (Bambusa arundinacea (Retz.) Willd.)* found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Vamsalochana (Bambusa arundinacea (Retz.) Willd.)</i> in authentic reference	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Siliceous Crystals	+	[Fig. 2.a]
2.	Rosset crystals	+	[Fig. 2.b]

- Absent, + Present

Table No. 4: Microscopic features in reference standard⁴ compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Pippali (Piper longum L.)* found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Pippali (Piper longum L.)</i> in authentic reference	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Stone cells	+	[Fig. 3.a]
2.	Starch grains	+	[Fig. 3.b]
3.	Fragments of thin-walled cells	+	[Fig. 3.c]
4.	Multicellular trichomes	+	[Fig. 3.d]

- Absent, + Present

Table No. 5: Microscopic features in reference standard⁵ compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Ela (Elettaria cardamomum (L.) Maton)* found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Ela (Elettaria cardamomum (L.) Maton)</i> in authentic reference	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Epidermal cells	+	[Fig. 4.a]
2.	Schlerenchyma of testa	+	[Fig. 4.b]
3.	Parenchymatous cells of the perispermprisms	+	[Fig. 4.c]
3.	Red coloured schlerenchymatous cells	+	[Fig. 4.d]
4.	Minute calcium oxalate crystals	+	[Fig. 4.e]

- Absent, + Present

Table No. 6: Microscopic features in reference standard⁶ compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Twak (Cinamonum verum J.S.Presl)* found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Twak (Cinamonum verum J.S.Presl)</i> in authentic reference	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Fibres	+	[Fig. 5.a]
2.	Starch grains	+	[Fig. 5.b]
3.	Sclereids	+	[Fig. 5.c]
4.	Phloem parenchyma	+	[Fig. 5.d]
5.	Vessel fragments	+	[Fig. 5.e]
6.	Oil cells	-	-
6.	Stone cells	-	-
7.	Small acicular raphides	-	-

- Absent, + Present

For this microscopic study, powder of *Sitopaladi Churna* was selected. The powder microscopic characters of *Sitopaladi Churna* were observed which will be narrated further. Powder microscopy of *Sitopaladi Churna* shows, presence of profound Starch grains suggests that it contains *Sitopala (Sachharum officinarum Linn.)*; presence of Siliceous crystals and rosette crystals, suggests that it contains *Vamsalochana (Bambusa arundinacea (Retz.) Willd.)*; presence of stone cells, starch grains, fragments of thin walled cells and multicellular trichomes suggests it contains *Pippali (Piper longum)*; and presence Epidermal cells, Schlerenchyma of testa, Parenchymatous cells of the perisperm prisms and red coloured schlerenchymatous cells suggests it contains *Ela (Elettaria cardamomum (L.) Maton)*, Fibres, Starch grains, Sclereids, Phloem parenchyma and vessel fragments shows presence of *Twak (Cinamonum verum J.S.Presl)* as its ingredients. But absence of oil globules suggest that exhausted ingredients can be adulterated with it.

CONCLUSION:

Sitopala (Sachharum officinarum Linn.), *Vamsalochana (Bambusa arundinacea (Retz.) Willd.)*, *Pippali (Piper longum)*, *Ela (Elettaria cardamomum (L.) Maton)* and *Twak (Cinamonum verum J.S.Presl)* are included in *Sitopaladi Churna* compound.

Key identifications of features of *Sitopala (Sachharum officinarum Linn.)*, *Vamsalochana (Bambusa arundinacea (Retz.) Willd.)*, *Pippali (Piper longum L.)*, *Ela (Elettaria cardamomum (L.) Maton)* and *Twak (Cinamonum verum J.S.Presl)* are as following:

Sr. no.	Plant	Key identification features
1.	<i>Sitopala</i> (<i>Sachharum officinarum</i> Linn.)	Starch grains, Crystals of calcium oxalate
2.	<i>Vamsalochana</i> (<i>Bambusa arundinacea</i> (Retz.) Willd.)	Siliceous Crystals, Rosset crystals
3.	<i>Pippali</i> (<i>Piper longum</i> L.)	Stone cells, starch grains, fragments of thin-walled cells and multicellular trichomes
4.	<i>Ela</i> (<i>Elettaria cardamomum</i> (L.) Maton)	Epidermal cells, schlerenchyma of testa, parenchymatous cells of the perisperm with prisms, red coloured schlerenchymatous cells, minute calcium oxalate crystals
5.	<i>Twak</i> (<i>Cinamonum verum</i> J.S.Presl)	Fibres, lignified stone cells, pitted parenchyma and acicular crystals of calcium oxalate

The market sample procured from the markets of Vadodara, Gujarat, India, contains *Sitopala* (*Sachharum officinarum* Linn.), *Pippali* (*Piper longum* L.), *Ela* (*Elettaria cardamomum* (L.) Maton) and *Twak* (*Cinamonum verum* J.S.Presl) as its ingredients. But absence of oil globules suggest that exhausted ingredients can be adulterated with it. Presence of siliceous crystals and rosette crystals, suggests that it contains *Vamsalochana* (*Bambusa arundinacea* (Retz.) Willd.) but difficult to differentiate with highly adulterated silica.

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Plate No. 1: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Sitopaladi Churna – Sitopala (Sachharum officinarum Linn.)*

Fig. 1(a). Starch grains

Fig. 1(b). Crystals of calcium oxalate

Plate No. 2: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Sitopaladi Churna – Vamsalochana (Bambusa arundinacea (Retz.) Willd.)*

Fig. 2(a). Siliceous Crystals

Fig. 2(b). Rosette Crystals

Plate No. 3: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Sitopaladi Churna – Pippali (Piper longum L.)*

Fig. 3(a). Stone cells

Fig. 3(b) Starch grains

Fig. 3(c). Fragments of thin-walled cells

Fig. 3(d). Multicellular trichome

Plate No. 4: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Sitopaladi Churna – Ela (Elettaria cardamomum (L.) Maton)*

Fig. 4(a). Epidermal cells

Fig. 4(b). Schlerenchyma of testa

Fig. 4(c). Parenchymatous cells of the perisperm with prism

Fig. 4(d). Red coloured schlerenchymatous cells

Fig. 4(e). Minute calcium oxalate crystals

Plate No. 5: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Sitopaladi Churna* – *Twak* (*Cinamonum verum* J.S.Presl)

Fig. 5(a). Fibre fragment

Fig. 5(b). Starch grains

Fig. 5(c). Sclereids

Fig. 5(d). Phloem parenchyma

Fig. 5(e). Vessel fragments

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